

Gene List for Analysis

1. Negative Controls: Housekeeping Genes

Ribosomal Large Subunit

RPL3, RPL4, RPL5, RPL6, RPL7, RPL7A, RPL8, RPL9, RPL10, RPL10A, RPL11, RPL12, RPL13, RPL13A, RPL14, RPL15, RPL17, RPL18, RPL18A, RPL19, RPL21, RPL22, RPL23, RPL23A

Ribosomal Small Subunit

RPS2, RPS3, RPS3A, RPS4X, RPS4Y1, RPS5, RPS6, RPS7, RPS8, RPS9, RPS10, RPS11, RPS12, RPS13, RPS14, RPS15, RPS15A, RPS16, RPS17, RPS18, RPS19, RPS20, RPS21

Cytoskeletal Proteins: Actin

ACTB, ACTG1, ACTA1, ACTA2, ACTC1, ACTN1, ACTN2, ACTN4, PFN1, PFN2

Cytoskeletal Proteins: Tubulin

TUBA1A, TUBA1B, TUBA1C, TUBA3C, TUBA3D, TUBA4A, TUBA8, TUBB, TUBB1, TUBB2A, TUBB2B, TUBB3, TUBB4A, TUBB4B, TUBB6

Glycolysis

HK1, HK2, GPI, PFKM, PFKP, PFKL, ALDOA, ALDOB, ALDOC, TP11, GAPDH, PGK1, PGK2, PGAM1, PGAM2, ENO1, ENO2, ENO3, PKM, PKLR, LDHA, LDHB, LDHC

TCA Cycle

CS, ACO1, ACO2, IDH1, IDH2, IDH3A, IDH3B, IDH3G, OGDH, SUCLA2, SUCLG1, SUCLG2, SDHA, SDHB, SDHC, SDHD, FH, MDH1, MDH2

Mitochondrial Respiratory Chain: Complex I

NDUFA1, NDUFA2, NDUFA3, NDUFA4, NDUFA5, NDUFA6, NDUFA7, NDUFA8, NDUFA9, NDUFA10, NDUFA11, NDUFA12, NDUFA13, NDUFB1, NDUFB2, NDUFB3, NDUFB4, NDUFB5, NDUFB6

Mitochondrial Respiratory Chain: Complex IV

COX4I1, COX4I2, COX5A, COX5B, COX6A1, COX6A2, COX6B1, COX6B2, COX6C, COX7A1, COX7A2, COX7A2L, COX7B, COX7C, COX8A, COX8C

ATP Synthase

ATP5F1A, ATP5F1B, ATP5F1C, ATP5F1D, ATP5F1E, ATP5MC1, ATP5MC2, ATP5MC3, ATP5MD, ATP5ME, ATP5MF, ATP5MG, ATP5PB, ATP5PD, ATP5PF, ATP5PO

Heat Shock Proteins

HSPA1A, HSPA1B, HSPA1L, HSPA2, HSPA4, HSPA4L, HSPA5, HSPA6, HSPA8, HSPA9, HSPA12A, HSPA12B, HSPA13, HSP90AA1, HSP90AB1, HSP90B1, HSPH1

2. Monoaminergic Systems (Controls)

Dopamine Receptors

DRD1, DRD2, DRD3, DRD4, DRD5

Dopamine Synthesis and Metabolism

TH, DDC, COMT, MAOA, MAOB, DBH, GCH1, PTS, QDPR, SPR

Dopamine Transport and Signaling

SLC6A3, SLC18A1, SLC18A2, PPP1R1B, GNAL, ADCY5, PDE1B, PDE10A

Serotonin Receptors

HTR1A, HTR1B, HTR1D, HTR1E, HTR1F, HTR2A, HTR2B, HTR2C, HTR3A, HTR3B, HTR3C, HTR3D, HTR3E, HTR4, HTR5A, HTR5BP, HTR6, HTR7

Serotonin Synthesis and Metabolism

TPH1, TPH2, SLC6A4, AANAT, ASMT

Norepinephrine Receptors

ADRA1A, ADRA1B, ADRA1D, ADRA2A, ADRA2B, ADRA2C, ADRB1, ADRB2, ADRB3

Norepinephrine Synthesis and Transport

PNMT, SLC6A2

Histamine System

HRH1, HRH2, HRH3, HRH4, HDC, HNMT, SLC22A3

Trace Amine-Associated Receptors

TAAR1, TAAR2, TAAR5, TAAR6, TAAR8, TAAR9

Downstream Signaling Molecules

GNB1, GNB2, GNB3, GNB4, GNB5, GNG2, GNG3, GNG4, GNG7, GNG11, GNG12, ADCY1, ADCY2, ADCY7, ADCY8, ADCY9, PDE4A, PDE4B, PDE4C, PDE4D

Vesicular Machinery

SYT1, SYT2, SYT4, SYT7, SYT11, SNAP25, VAMP2, STX1A, STX1B, CPLX1, CPLX2

3. Mosaic Chromosomal Alteration (mCA)-Related Genes

DNA Damage Response and Repair

ATM, TREX1, ATMIN

Cell Cycle Regulation and Mitosis

MAD1L1, CENPN, PMF1, TPX2, NPAT

Apoptosis and Cell Survival

TP53, BCL2, BCL2L1, TCL1A

Hematopoietic Signaling

MPL, JAK2

Epigenetic Regulation

TET2, DNMT3A

Telomere Maintenance

TERT

Transcription Factors in Hematopoiesis

FLI1, GATA2, RUNX1

Mosaic Loss of Y Chromosome (mLOY)-Associated Genes

TSC22D2, SEMA4A, SMPD2, QKI, NREP, DLK1, RBPMS, SETBP1, SENP7, WBP4

Chromosome X Loss-Associated Genes

SP140L, HLA-B

mCA Expansion Modulators

NRIP1

Additional mCA-Associated Genes

DCPS, ADAM17, PPP1R16B, OR4C16

4. Mitotic Stress Pathway Genes

Spindle Assembly Checkpoint (SAC)

MAD1L1, MAD2L1, BUB1, BUB1B, BUB3, TTK, CDC20

Centrosome and Spindle Regulators

AURKA, AURKB, TPX2, PLK1, PLK4, CEP55, TACC3

Kinetochores and Microtubule Dynamics

CENPA, CENPB, KIF2C, KIF11, DLGAP5, PRC1, NDC80

Cell Cycle Regulators in Mitosis

CDK1, CCNB1, FOXM1, UBE2C, TOP2A, PCNA

DNA Damage Response Genes Active in Mitosis

ATM, ATR, CHEK1, CHEK2, TP53, TP53BP1, BRCA1, BRCA2, MDC1, H2AFX

Other Mitotic Stress-Associated Genes

SFN, DMAP1, PARK7, BIRC5, NEK2, MASTL

5. Clonal Hematopoiesis Pathway Genes

Epigenetic Regulators in Clonal Hematopoiesis

DNMT3A, TET2, ASXL1, IDH1, IDH2, EZH2

Spliceosome Components

SF3B1, SRSF2, U2AF1, ZRSR2, SRSF1, U2AF2, PRPF8, LUC7L2

DNA Damage Response in Clonal Hematopoiesis

TP53, PPM1D, CHEK2, ATM, BRCC3

Signaling Pathway Genes

JAK2, CBL, KRAS, NRAS, PTPN11, GNB1, FLT3, KIT, MPL

Transcription Factors in Clonal Hematopoiesis

RUNX1, WT1, GATA2, FOXP1, BCOR, BCORL1, CUX1, ETV6, CEBPA

Chromatin Modifiers

ARID2, CREBBP, KMT2C, SETD2, SETDB1, PHF6, ZBTB33

Additional Clonal Hematopoiesis Drivers

ABL2, TP63, NOTCH1, MYD88, STAT3, NF1, CALR

Cohesin Complex

RAD21, SMC1A, SMC3, STAG2

mCA-Associated Genes in Clonal Hematopoiesis

DCPS, ADAM17, PPP1R16B, OR4C16

Germline Susceptibility Loci

TERT, SP140L, HLA-B, TCL1A